

3-(*o*-Acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide. A Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Ni(II) and Cu(II) and Evaluation of Stepwise Formation Constants

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Manuscript received 4 October 1980, accepted 30 May 1983

Nickel(II) and copper(II) could be estimated spectrophotometrically with 3-(*o*-acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide within pH 6.6-10.4 and 7.0-10.6, respectively. The complexes extracted in chloroform are yellow and have $\lambda_{\max}$ at 430 nm (NiL₂) and 420 nm (CuL₂), respectively. The compositions determined by Job's and mole-ratio methods have also been verified from the respective $\bar{n}$ values. The Beer's law range, optimum concentration range, molar absorptivity and sensitivity for Ni(II) complex are 0.25-4.5 ppm, 0.5-4 ppm, 1.4×10^4 and $0.0042 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively and the same for Cu(II) complex are 0.25-4.7 ppm, 0.8-4.5 ppm, 1.21×10^4 and $0.0053 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The order of stability constants for Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes, calculated by Leden's and Yatsimirskii's methods agree with Irving-William's rule (Cu > Ni). Either ion could be estimated in presence of several foreign ions. The analytical precisions in terms of standard deviation are $\pm 0.26\%$ and $\pm 0.22\%$ for nickel estimations and copper estimations, respectively.

In addition to the several reagents¹⁻⁴ which produce colouration with Ni(II) and Cu(II) ions, the triazines as a class of interesting reagent are worth mentioning. Many of the triazines⁵⁻⁹ so far reported for the estimations have been found to have lower sensitivities in comparison to 3-(*o*-acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide, the reagent recommended in this paper. Moreover the pH ranges and occasionally the optimum concentration ranges were also found quite narrow.

The reagent has been reported for Co(II) determination earlier and its use has now been extended for nickel(II) and copper(II) estimations as well. The complexes formed by mixing the reactants are not very soluble in alcoholic medium but could be extracted quantitatively in chloroform and hence solvent extraction techniques were followed.

In addition to simple spectrophotometric determinations attempts have been made to find out stepwise formation constants K_1 and K_2 in each case from spectrophotometric data following the graphical extrapolation methods of Leden and Yatsimirskii.

Experimental

Materials and methods: The reagent 3-(*o*-acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide was prepared following the literature method⁹. The reagent solution (0.5 mg/ml) was prepared in absolute ethanol. The standard Ni(II) and Cu(II) solutions were made from nickel chloride (G.R., E. Merck) and electrolytically pure copper. The respective metal contents were determined by the Ni-DMG

method, and iodometrically. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from the chloride or nitrate salts of cations and from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts of anions of A.R. grade. Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out using a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with matched 1 cm glass cells. The pH values were adjusted with a Cambridge bench model pH meter.

Absorbance curves: 3.0 ml of 0.5 mg/ml ethanolic solution of the reagent were added to 3.0 ml of nickel(II) solution $\{[M]=0.025 \text{ mg/ml}\}$ and 2.5 ml of copper(II) solution $\{[M]=0.025 \text{ mg/ml}\}$, respectively followed by 5 ml of 1% Na-K-tartrate solution (aq). The pH of the resultant mixtures were adjusted with dilute alkali to ~ 8.5 and the mixtures allowed to stand for 30 min. The colloidal precipitates of both the complexes were extracted several times (3-4) with chloroform in presence of an electrolyte. The chloroform extracts were combined, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the final volume in each case was made upto 25 ml in a volumetric flask. The absorbances of the yellow coloured complexes in chloroform medium in both the cases were measured in the wavelength region 400-600 nm against reagent blank. The absorption maxima, $\lambda_{\max}$, were found at 430 and 420 nm for nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes, respectively.

Effect of pH and reagent concentration: The colour intensity of the complexes once formed remained constant at least for 36 hr for Ni(II) complex and 40 hr for Cu(II) complex within the respective pH ranges. The intensities of the colour systems developed with the same reagent concentrations, using 2 ppm metal concentration in each

case, at different pH within the ranges 6.6-10.4 and 7.0-10.6, respectively for nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes, were found to have fixed absorbance values. The minimum metal to ligand ratio to be maintained during complexation to produce maximum colour intensity in both the cases within the given pH ranges was found to be 1 : 10. Addition of more reagent (upto M : L=1 : 30) in either case did not produce any adverse effect on the colour system.

Beer's law range, optimum concentration range, molar absorptivity and sensitivity : It was found that Beer's law is obeyed over the $[Ni^{2+}]$ range 0.25-4.5 ppm. However, the optimum concentration range with the highest accuracy, as evaluated from Ringbom's¹⁰ curve was 0.5-4.0 ppm. The molar absorptivity of the complex as calculated from the Beer's law data and the photometric sensitivity according to Sandell¹¹ were found to be 1.4×10^4 and $0.0042 \mu g \text{ cm}^{-2}$ respectively, at 430 nm. The corresponding values for the copper(II) complex, determined in an identical manner, were 0.25-4.7 ppm, $0.8-4.5 \text{ ppm}$, 1.21×10^4 and $0.0053 \mu g \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively at 420 nm.

Composition of the complexes : In both the Job's¹² and the mole ratio¹³ methods, equimolecular concentration ($2.12 \times 10^{-4} M$ for $[Ni^{2+}]$ and $1.98 \times 10^{-4} M$ for $[Cu^{2+}]$) of the reactants were employed for studying the composition of the complexes. In either case the complex in solution contains metal and ligand in the ratio of 1 : 2. The composition of both nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes have also been verified from the respective $\bar{n}$ values, obtained by graphical differentiation of ϕ , the degree of complex formation, where $\bar{n}$ - average number of donor bound to the metal atom = $d \log \phi / d \log [L]$. The gradient of the tangent to the curve obtained by plotting the logarithm of degree of

complex formation (ϕ) vs the negative logarithm of equilibrium free-ligand concentration, pL , yields the value of $\bar{n}$. The highest values of $\bar{n}$ obtained in this way were 1.65 and 1.66 for nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes, respectively indicating the formation of ML_2 in solution.

Effect of diverse ions : Among the anions and complexing agents, EDTA interferes in both the cases seriously. Thiosulphate interferes with Cu(II) determination. 100 fold excess of thiosulphate could be tolerated in Ni(II) determination. 50 mg of N-K-tartrate is tolerable in both the determinations. Fluoride, phosphate, and borate upto 100 fold and citrate upto 50 fold excess are tolerated in either case. Co(II), Cr(III), Mn(II), Ce(IV), V(VI), Mo(VI), Pd(II) interfere with the determinations. Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), upto 15 times excess do not interfere in either case. Pb(II), Fe(III) interferences (15 fold excess) in both the cases could be overcome with NH_4OAc and NH_4HF_2 as masking agents, respectively. The determinations in both cases were carried out with 2 ppm of metal and a change of 0.005 in absorbance value was considered for reproducible results.

Evaluation of metal ligand formation constants : The stepwise stability constants were calculated pursuing the methods of Leden and Yatsimirskii as have been deduced¹⁴ in connection with the determination of cobalt(II).

Leden's method : In both the determinations, metal : ligand is 1 : 2. The degree of formation (ϕ) is therefore expressed as

$$\phi = 1 + K_1[L] + K_1K_2[L]^2$$

The coefficients K_1, K_2 of the variable $[L]$ are obtained by constructing suitable auxiliary functions (ψ_1, ψ_2) and extrapolations of this to zero value of the variable (Fig. 1),

Fig. 1. Leden's plot of subsidiary functions ψ_1 (a) and ψ_2 (b) as function of $[L]$.

 Fig. 2. Yatsimirskii's plot of subsidiary functions f_1 (a) and f_2 (b) as function of $[L]$.

$$\text{Thus } \psi_1 = \frac{\phi - 1}{[L]} = K_1 + K_1 K_2 [L]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \psi_1 &= \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\phi - 1}{[L]} = K_1 = C_1 \\ &= 0.80 \times 10^8 (\text{Ni}) = 1.5 \times 10^8 (\text{Cu}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \psi_2 &= \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\psi_1 - K_1}{[L]} = K_1 K_2 = C_2 \\ &= 0.48 \times 10^{10} (\text{Ni}) = 1.8 \times 10^{10} (\text{Cu}) \end{aligned}$$

The intercepts C_1 and C_2 on the ordinate are thus numerically equal to K_1 and $K_1 K_2$, respectively.

Yatsimirskii's method : The intercept values a_1 , a_2 and b_1 , b_2 (Figs. 2 and 3) related to $\bar{\epsilon}$, the mean molar extinction coefficients. Subsidiary functions f_1 , f_2 and g calculated by the usual methods for both the complexes are given as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} f_1 &= \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\bar{\epsilon}}{[L]} = a_1 = 0.11 \times 10^{10} (\text{Ni}), \\ &= 0.195 \times 10^{10} (\text{Cu}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} f_2 &= \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_1 - \bar{\epsilon}}{[L]} = a_2 = -0.037 \times 10^{15} (\text{Ni}), \\ &= -0.123 \times 10^{15} (\text{Cu}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} \bar{\epsilon} = b_1 = 0.13 \times 10^8 (\text{Ni}), = 0.13 \times 10^8 (\text{Cu})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} g &= \lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} \frac{\bar{\epsilon} - b_1}{Y} = b_2 = -0.064 (\text{Ni}), \\ &= -0.042 (\text{Cu}) \end{aligned}$$

The stepwise stability values were evaluated by substituting intercept values in the respective expressions, $K_1 = \frac{a_1 b_1 - a_2 b_2}{b_1^2 + a_1 b_2}$ and $K_2 = \frac{a_1^2 + a_2 b_1}{a_1 b_1 - a_2 b_2}$.

 Fig. 3. Yatsimirskii's plot, mean molar extinction coefficient $\bar{\epsilon}$ (a) and subsidiary function g (b) as function $Y (= \frac{1}{[L]})$.

The results have been recorded graphically, avoiding tabular representation, to study the characteristic nature of the different curves. Since the curves related to copper are almost identical in nature with those of nickel, the curves related to nickel determination have been reproduced only.

The stepwise stability constants, as determined for nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes, are summarised in Table 1. It is evident from the table that the respective values of Cu(II) complex are slightly higher than those of the Ni(II) complex, indicating thereby the conformity with Irving and William's¹⁶ rule i.e., Cu > Ni.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Ni(II) AND Cu(II) COMPLEXES AT 25°

Complex	Method	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
Nickel(II)	Leden's	4.90	4.78	9.68
	Yatsimirskii's	5.08	4.78	9.86
Copper(II)	Leden's	5.17	5.08	10.25
	Yatsimirskii's	5.84	5.02	10.86

Analytical precision : 2 ppm of metal in both the cases in 16 determinations each have been determined with a standard deviation of ± 0.26 and $\pm 0.22\%$ for nickel(II) and copper(II) estimations, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi for a Teacher Fellowship to one of them (N.R.B.) under F.I. Programme.

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